

Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM

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Risk Mitigation in Open Access to Digital Cultural Heritage Collections

What is the Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM?

Making digital cultural heritage collections openly available for everyone to use is not without its challenges. Concerns around copyright compliance, privacy protection, ethical representation, financial sustainability, and technical limitations, particularly in an age of uncertainty, often deter institutions from embracing openness. The Risk Management Toolkit for Open [GLAM](#) ↗ (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) is designed to support and equip GLAM professionals with the tools they need to confidently share their collections with the world.

The Toolkit is a living resource that brings together a wide range of curated materials and good practices to help mitigate the risks associated with open access to digital cultural heritage collections. Within the context of this Toolkit, “open” refers to free and unrestricted access to works made available under open-compliant licences and tools, without technological barriers, in alignment with the [Open Definition 2.1](#) ↗ of the Open Knowledge Foundation, and broader clarifications of open standards, as captured in Andrea Wallace’s [“Clarifying ‘Open’”](#) ↗ (2020).

The Toolkit was originally developed based on findings from research conducted in 2024 within the [Creative Commons Open Culture Platform](#) ↗. This [blog post](#) ↗ outlines the full background, including links to the project report and other accompanying documents. Since then, the Toolkit’s authors have reviewed and expanded the content, with all changes documented in the [version history](#).

Who is this Toolkit for?

The Toolkit can be useful to GLAM professionals and volunteers working in memory institutions or community heritage initiatives, interested in open culture, and responsible for digitising, curating, cataloguing and making digital cultural heritage collections available to the public. GLAM professionals and volunteers include but are not limited to:

- digital archivists,
- librarians,
- collection managers,
- digitisation specialists,
- technicians,
- metadata specialists,
- rights and reproductions managers,
- copyright officers,
- preservation specialists,
- project managers,
- digital content curators.

How to use this Toolkit?

- Browse the risk areas to learn more about key challenges, mitigation strategies, practical tools and resources, and inspiring good practices.
- Follow the recommended strategies and selected practices to manage risks effectively within your organisation's open access programme.
- Explore the use cases in each risk area to see whether any apply to your local context, or visit the "Use cases" section for a complete list organised by collection type.
- Revise and adapt the provided templates to meet your specific needs and institutional requirements.

- Consult the related resources to deepen understanding of risk management in open access to digital cultural heritage.

Reading risks as an interconnected system

The risks outlined in this Toolkit are interdependent rather than isolated. Decisions taken in one area -such as licensing, infrastructure investment, or community engagement- inevitably shape exposure in others. Effective risk management for open access to digital cultural heritage therefore requires coordinated, cross-functional approaches rather than siloed solutions.

The Toolkit aims to cultivate and promote a more nuanced understanding of these risks and challenges, and to share information on potential mitigation strategies. Its content is not, and cannot be, comprehensive. The authors do not advocate for any single approach; rather, the insights and curated resources reflect the existing literature and the practices of a diverse range of institutions working within their own contexts.

Open invitation to contribute

If you have any suggestions to improve the Toolkit content, please [contact us ↗](#). We would appreciate your help in making the Toolkit more inclusive by incorporating diverse resources, use cases and policy templates, representing a broader range of institutions, collections and communities from different regions.

Note that to ensure the Toolkit remains an open and community-focused resource, we prioritise materials that are freely accessible, non-commercial and sustainable over time. Where possible, we seek to limit the inclusion of paid resources, proprietary tools or content that primarily promotes fee-based services and other commercial offerings. Where appropriate, preference is given to materials with ongoing value -such as open educational resources, recurring training programmes, and maintained online guidance- rather than one-off events or time-limited offerings.

Version history

v2.0 (current version) - December 23, 2025 | Full Toolkit revision and update, including the addition of the Geopolitical Risk Area and the Risk-Strategy Interrelation Matrix.

v1.1 (pre-v2.0 release) - October 21, 2025 | Addition of draft Geopolitical Risk Area – open for community feedback (public consultation period: October 22 – November 30, 2025). This version also introduced a Name Policy, allowing contributors to choose if and how they are credited.

v1.0 - December 13, 2024 | Published first time.

Risk Area: Legal

Copyright and privacy considerations

GLAM institutions face significant legal challenges, particularly in determining copyright ownership and ensuring compliance with copyright laws. Concerns are frequently raised about the potential misuse of open access materials and the risk of infringements due to incorrect licensing. Additionally, many institutions note the complexities of managing copyrighted materials they do not own, emphasising the need for cautious handling to avoid legal complications.

"We aren't always the copyright holders on all works and/or their reproductions. In other cases, we manage the digital reproductions but are not the owner of the underlying works."

Non-profit organisation, Belgium

Key Risks

- Compliance with copyright laws, particularly regarding works with ambiguous ownership or uncertain copyright status, such as orphan works and out-of-commerce works.
- Compliance with cultural heritage laws that extend control over cultural heritage materials through copyright-like restrictions beyond the scope or term of copyright law.
- Compliance with contractual restrictions or licence terms that override or conflict with statutory exceptions and limitations to copyright, or with protections of the public domain.
- Protection of sensitive personal information found within collection records, such as donor details and subject data.
- Adherence to third-party terms of service for platforms or tools used to host or share collections.

Mitigation Strategies

Related mitigation strategies

For organisational policies, workflows, and governance structures that support consistent copyright compliance, privacy protection, and takedown procedures, see the [Policy Risk Area](#).

For risks arising from political interference, jurisdictional changes, sanctions, censorship demands, or conflict-driven disruptions that may affect legal compliance, or enforcement capacity, see the [Geopolitical Risk Area](#).

- **Conduct a copyright and rights audit:** Review the collection to determine copyright status, ownership, and rights holders for each item. This ensures that items shared online are legally compliant.
- **Implement clear licensing:** Apply standardised copyright licenses, public domain tools, and rights statements carefully, ensuring accurate attribution and clear usage guidelines to minimise the risk of misuse.
- **Provide copyright training for staff:** Ensure that team members involved in digitising and licensing/labelling are well-trained in copyright and licensing principles to avoid potential infringements.
- **Develop infringement response protocols:** Establish protocols to handle copyright claims or misuse reports promptly and transparently – e.g., by developing open access and takedown policies.
- **Safeguard privacy:** Identify and protect personal and sensitive data within the collection records, ensuring that any personal information (such as names or contact information of donors or subjects) is either anonymised or redacted before public sharing.
- **Review third-party terms of service:** Regularly review and ensure compliance with the terms of service of any third-party platforms or digital tools used for hosting, sharing, or distributing collections.

- **Licensing/rights statements:** Copyright licenses and public domain tools like those from [Creative Commons ↗](#) or the [Rights Statements Consortium ↗](#) can help generate clear and machine-readable [CC licenses ↗](#) or [Rights Statements ↗](#) based on each item's copyright and reuse status.
 - Creative Commons Guide - [Recommended Licenses and Tools for Cultural Heritage Content ↗](#)
 - [Creative Commons License Chooser ↗](#)
 - Europeana's Guide - [How to select an accurate rights statement ↗](#)
 - [Rights Statements ↗](#) - 3 categories, 12 different Rights Statements
 - GLAM-E Lab's Handbook: [Selecting an Alternative Label or Licence ↗](#)
- **Legal and privacy compliance templates:** Use standardised checklists and templates for copyright clearance, permissions, licensing agreements, and privacy notices to ensure consistency across the collections.
 - Naomi Korn Associates's [Copyright Rights Clearance Checklists ↗](#)
 - Naomi Korn Associates's [Creative Commons Licences: A Guide to Data Protection & Copyright ↗](#) (including checklists and templates)
 - GLAM-E Lab's [Copyright Clearance Handbook for Public Domain Publications of Digital Collections ↗](#)
 - GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Copyright Clearance Log ↗](#)
 - [Simplified flowchart for licensing in the context of Brazil ↗](#)
 - [Takedown Policy template ↗](#) of the Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM.
- **Copyright training for GLAM professionals:**
 - [Creative Commons Certificate Programme ↗](#) - Open Culture/GLAM section ([Certificate resources ↗](#)). Creative Commons also provides [customised training and consulting ↗](#) offerings.
 - [How to identify and clear copyright in collection items ↗](#) - This page by Europeana shares training to help GLAM professionals determine if, and which rights exist in their institution's collection items. It is the first of three blocks of training, followed by [Training on the available rights statements ↗](#) used by Europeana and [Training on how to select an accurate rights statement ↗](#).

- Self-paced courses on the [Europeana Academy](#) ↗ training platform:
 - [Copyright when sharing data with Europeana](#) ↗ - This course shares training to help you determine if, and which, rights exist in your collection items. This is an essential first step before one can assign an accurate rights statement. It is the first of three blocks of training, and is followed by the course on the available rights statements used by Europeana and the course on how to select an accurate rights statement.
 - [Understanding the standardised rights information used by Europeana](#) ↗ - Rights statements express the copyright status of a digital object and provide information about how someone can re-use the object. This course outlines and offers training on the rights statements you can apply to the data you share with Europeana.
 - [How to select an accurate rights statement](#) ↗ - This self-paced course offers information on how to identify the most accurate and adequate rights statement for the data you share with Europeana.
- Courses on the WikiLearn platform:
 - [Introduktion till upphovsrätt](#) ↗ (Swedish) - The course (developed by Wikimedia Sverige) provides a brief introduction to copyright, Creative Commons licenses, and what you need to consider when contributing to Wikimedia's projects.
 - [Propriété intellectuelle et Créative Commons](#) ↗ (French) - This course, which is designed for Wikimedians and their partners (for example, staff of cultural institutions), provides an introduction to key concepts of copyright and how to use Creative Commons licenses.
 - [Wikimedia Core Curriculum module 5: Copyright and free licenses](#) ↗ (English) - This course describes traditional copyright, discusses its shortcomings, and introduces alternative licenses (in particular the Creative Commons licenses).
- **Other resources:**
 - [Law Flow – Simplified Legal Complexity](#) ↗ is a website that offers a clear and accessible way to navigate legal complexity through flowcharts. It covers a wide range of legal topics, with a particular focus on intellectual property law in the European Union.

- [CopyrightUser.EU](#) ↗ is an independent online platform intended to make EU copyright law accessible to everyone.
- [CopyrightUser.org](#) ↗ is an online resource aimed at making UK copyright law accessible to creators, media professionals, entrepreneurs, students, and members of the public.
- The [copyrightexceptions.eu](#) ↗ is a collaborative effort to map user rights in the European Union's copyright framework.

Good Practices

- **Stay updated with good practices:** Follow organisations and initiatives like [Creative Commons](#) ↗, [Europeana](#) ↗, [OpenGLAM](#) ↗, and [GLAM Wiki](#) ↗ to stay updated with open access guidelines.
- **Create user guidelines for open content:** Provide clear guidelines on how users may interact with open access collections, respecting legal and ethical boundaries.
 - [Public Domain Guidelines](#) ↗ - Use guidelines, information-only draft on CC Wiki
 - [Nudging Users to Reference Institutions with Public Domain Materials: A Creative Commons Guide](#) ↗ (English) – Available in other languages [here](#) ↗.
- **Build a community of practice:** Join forums and networks with other GLAM institutions to share experiences, insights, and risk management strategies.
 - Become a [member](#) ↗ of the [Creative Commons Open Culture Platform](#) ↗, where you can be added to the mailing list, and can join regular meetings and work together on collaborative projects to further Open Culture.
 - Join the [Europeana Copyright community](#) ↗ (i.e. group of professionals interested in copyright and digital cultural heritage), so as to stay informed about copyright trends, legal and policy changes, rights information and approaches to clearing rights.
 - Join the [Cultural Heritage Open Scholarship Network](#) ↗ (CHOSN) to share knowledge on how to establish good practices in open scholarship.

How this risk area connects to other risk areas

Legal clarity underpins all other risk mitigation efforts. Unclear copyright status, restrictive contracts, or weak privacy safeguards can amplify financial risks (unexpected liabilities), ethical risks (harm to communities), technical risks (forced takedowns or platform dependency), and geopolitical risks (external leverage through legal pressure). Strong rights audits, transparent licensing, and privacy protocols reduce institutional exposure across all risk areas and increase resilience in times of crisis.

Use cases

Cultural heritage professionals don't make certain digital collections open access because of copyright ambiguity. If materials are made available without proper copyright checks, there's a risk of copyright infringement or misuse by the public, which can impact legal compliance and damage the reputation of the institution.

Decision makers don't make certain digital collections open access, because inaccurate licensing or uncertainties in copyright ownership could lead to privacy breaches or unauthorised sharing or misuse. This would impact the institution's ability to safeguard sensitive cultural materials and comply with contractual obligations, especially in cases involving Indigenous communities.

Risk Area: Ethical

Ethical and cultural sensitivities

The ethical handling of sensitive collections, particularly those related to Indigenous cultural heritage, is a significant concern. Institutions usually emphasise the importance of culturally sensitive protocols to manage public access, ensuring respect for community ownership, self-image rights, and ethical representation within digital spaces.

"Our images of our collection appear on foreign websites who use it for their products. We also do not want our images to be used with misleading/incorrect information."

Museum, United Kingdom

Key Risks

- Ethical issues regarding culturally sensitive materials, including Indigenous cultural heritage, and materials related to historically contested or traumatic experiences.
- Risks of misrepresentation or disrespect to communities connected to the collections.

Mitigation Strategies

Related mitigation strategies

For formal policies, legal safeguards, and documented procedures that support ethical decision-making, accountability, and community protocols, see the [Policy](#) and [Legal](#) Risk Areas.

For guidance on managing ethical risks under political pressure, conflict, censorship, or crisis -particularly where narratives, representation, or community relationships are contested- see the [Geopolitical Risk Area](#).

- **Community consultations:** Engage with communities to gain insights into how materials should be represented and shared.
- **Develop sensitivity protocols:** Establish protocols for handling sensitive content, including restrictions on certain types of usage or visibility if requested by communities.
- **Implement cultural guidance in metadata:** Incorporate metadata tags/labels to indicate culturally sensitive content, and recommended use practices, enhancing respectful interaction with the material.
- **Provide ethical training for staff:** Ensure team members understand ethical considerations around cultural heritage and the importance of cultural protocols and norms.
- **Review social/community norms of third-party platforms:** Regularly review and ensure compliance with the social/community norms of any third-party platforms or digital tools used for hosting, sharing, or distributing collections.

- **Cultural protocol guidelines:** Available through consultations with communities, offering guidance on ethically managing cultural collections.
 - [CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance](#)
 - [Ethical Sharing Card Game](#) by the Ethics of Open Sharing Working Group of the Creative Commons Open Culture Platform for navigating ethical considerations.
 - General guide on how to play the game available on this [Medium article](#).
 - Webinar: [Ethics of Open Sharing with Creative Commons & Wiki Loves Living Heritage](#)
 - Anderson, J. (2006), [Cultural Protocols: A Framework](#), Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (including a protocol template for a digital archive, pp. 28-31).
 - Creative Australia's [Protocols for using First Nations Intellectual and Cultural Property in the Arts](#).
 - Janke, T. (2019) [Protocols for Using First Nations Cultural and Intellectual Property in the Arts](#), Australia Council for the Arts
 - [The Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Protocols for Libraries, Archives and Information Services](#)
 - [ENRICH: Equity for Indigenous Research and Innovation Coordinating Hub](#)
 - First Nations Information Governance Centre: [The First Nations Principles of OCAP](#)
 - [Indigitization Toolkit](#): Tools for Digitizing and Sustaining Indigenous Knowledge
 - ARIPO: African Regional Intellectual Property Organization (2010) [Swakopmund Protocol on the Protection of Traditional Knowledge and Expressions of Folklore](#).
 - [Anti-Racism Toolkit](#) – Books, resources, and links to help fight racism. This is a living document maintained by Georgetown University Library that serves as a launching point for more extensive study and action.

- [Asian American and Pacific Islander Toolkit ↗](#) – Books, resources, and links to help fight racism in regard to Asian American and Pacific Islander communities. This is a living document maintained by Georgetown University Library that serves as a launching point for more extensive study and action.
- [Indigenous Voices, Lives, & Issues Toolkit ↗](#) – Books, resources, and links on the lives, experiences, and challenges of the Indigenous Peoples of Turtle Island (North America). This is a living document maintained by Georgetown University Library that serves as a launching point for more extensive study and action.
- [Words Matter: An Unfinished Guide to Word Choices in the Cultural Sector ↗](#) – The publication explains that the description of an object has just as much meaning as the object itself. It aims to help understand why a word that has no connotations for one person is particularly sensitive to another.
- [Archiving as a Collective Practice: A Guide from the Palestinian Feminist Archive Berlin ↗](#) (in German): Developed as part of Wikimedia Germany's [re•shape ↗](#) programme, this guide documents and contextualises the archival practice of a Palestinian-feminist collective in Germany, outlining its methods, ethical foundations, and engagement with anti-colonial remembrance in the Palestinian diaspora. It also includes [resources ↗](#) on archiving the knowledge of marginalised communities online.
- **Recommendations for Holocaust Material Evidence and Testimony:** Available by the [Digital Holocaust Memory Project ↗](#) (most recent work: [Landecker Digital Memory Lab ↗](#))
 - Recommendations for Digitising Material Evidence of the Holocaust (available [here ↗](#) and [here ↗](#)).
 - Recommendations for Digitally Recording, Recirculating and Remixing Holocaust Testimony (available [here ↗](#) and [here ↗](#)).
- **Sensitivity labeling in metadata:** Use labels to flag sensitive items and guide users on appropriate use.
 - [Traditional Knowledge \(TK\) Labels ↗](#) by Local Contexts
 - Collections Trust's [Decolonising the Database ↗](#) resources

- [DE-BIAS Project ↗](#) to detect and curate harmful language in cultural heritage collections. They promote a more inclusive and respectful approach to the description of digital collections and the telling of stories and histories of minority communities.
- Reparative Archival Description Working Group: [Guiding Principles ↗](#); [Recommendations ↗](#); [Standardized Descriptive Notes ↗](#) maintained by Yale University Library. Reparative Archival Description aims to remediate or contextualise potentially outdated or harmful language used in archival description and to create archival description that is accurate, inclusive, and community-centered.
- [SABIO - The SociAI Bias Observatory project ↗](#) aims to create a knowledge graph on top of existing collection databases that makes prejudices and imbalances in the data explicit such that they can be addressed, as well as taken into account by users of the data.
- **Open source collection management systems:** There are options for managing and sharing digital collections ethically.
 - [Mukurtu CMS ↗](#) – free, mobile, and open source platform built with Indigenous communities to manage and share digital cultural heritage.

Good Practices

- The Museums Association's [Code of Ethics for Museums](#) provides a framework for the practical application of ethical considerations to everyday work in museums and reflects a contract of trust between museums and the public.
- The Archives and Records Association's [Code of Ethics](#) sets out the standards of professional behaviour expected of archivists, archive conservators, records managers and those occupied in related activities, who are individual members of the Archives and Records Association (UK and Ireland).
- The Oral History Society's [legal and ethical guidance](#) is for people who record oral history interviews, and organisations and individuals who keep collections of oral history recordings in the four nations of the United Kingdom -England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland- which together operate under three legal systems.
- Local Contexts's Traditional Knowledge [Labels](#) allow communities to express local and specific conditions for sharing and engaging in future research and relationships in ways that are consistent with already existing community rules, governance, and protocols for using, sharing, and circulating knowledge and data. The [Notices](#) are tools for institutions and researchers to identify Indigenous collections and data, and recognise Indigenous rights and interests.
- [The He Korahi Māori Framework at Auckland Museum](#) sets out a strategic pathway towards achieving the bicultural aspirations of Auckland War Memorial Museum, and to embed in all their activities the spirit of partnership and goodwill envisaged by the Treaty of Waitangi.
- [The Teu Le Vā Framework at Auckland Museum](#) outlines what Auckland Museum means by "creating a strong Pacific dimension". The aim is to better reflect Auckland's rich, contemporary Pacific culture, and improve the under-representation of visitation by Pacific people and increase their engagement with Museum programmes.
- [Indigenous Archives Collective](#) is a group of researchers and practitioners –both Indigenous and non-Indigenous– who came together to revitalise the Collective, and reframe the site as an open blog to encourage discussion about Indigenous archives.

- [The Mukurtu Showcase ↗](#) is a grassroots project aiming to empower communities to manage, share, narrate, and exchange their digital heritage in culturally relevant and ethically-minded ways. The Mukurtu Community showcase their sites and their stories on this website.
- [Native-Land.ca ↗](#) is a web-based resource created in 2015 by Victor Temprano (and now a part of Native Land Digital) to draw attention to the importance of land and territories and the histories of colonization that have systematically dispossessed Indigenous peoples of their land.
- [Palestine Open Maps ↗](#) is developed by Ahmad Barclay, Majd Al-shihabi, Hanan Yazigi, Morad Taleeb, Henry Zaccak, and Bassam Barham, Palestine Open Maps is a platform that uses maps and data to retrace the transformation of human and natural geography in Palestine.
- [Plateau Peoples' Web Portal ↗](#) is a collaboration between the Spokane Tribe of Indians, the Confederated Tribes Of The Colville Reservation, the Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation, the Coeur d'Alene Tribe of Indians, the Confederated Tribes of Warm Springs, the Confederated Tribes and Bands of the Yakama Nation, The Confederated Salish and Kootenai Tribes of the Flathead Reservation, the Nez Perce Tribe, the Center for Digital Scholarship and Curation and Native American Programs at Washington State University. The Portal aggregates cultural materials from multiple repositories that have been chosen and curated by tribal representatives.
- The Clark Art Institute in Williamstown, Massachusetts issued a [statement ↗](#) disapproving the reuse of Jean-Léon Gérôme's painting "Slave Market" (1866) by the German right-wing party Alternative für Deutschland (AfD), while still enacting an Open Access policy, allowing for any reproduction of a public domain work to be downloaded high-resolution for free, as expressed in their [FAQ page ↗](#).
- [Curationist.org ↗](#)'s [approach to metadata ↗](#) provides comprehensive information about why metadata is important and how they work with it.

How this risk area connects to other risk areas

Ethical risks intersect closely with legal compliance, policy development, and geopolitical pressures. Decisions about openness, restriction, or representation - particularly for Indigenous or contested collections- must be supported by clear governance, legally sound frameworks, and culturally informed metadata. In crisis contexts, ethical commitments can be challenged by political or financial pressure, making early community engagement and documented protocols essential safeguards.

Use cases

Curators don't make Indigenous collections open access, because there is a risk of unethical sharing without proper decolonial protocols. This could lead to cultural exploitation and disrespect towards the communities, undermining trust and collaboration with Indigenous partners.

Institution managers don't make certain heritage photographs open access, because of potential self-image rights violations and misuse for commercial purposes. This can harm the dignity of the individuals depicted and damage the institution's commitment to ethical and respectful representation.

Digital collection managers don't make certain culturally sensitive audio and video materials open access, because there's a risk of them being exploited for commercial purposes without permission. This could disrespect the cultural heritage of the content and negatively affect the institution's relationships with content owners and the public.

Data managers don't make certain open datasets available without restrictions, because the information could be misused for illicit excavations or fuel conspiracy theories. This misuse can lead to cultural misinformation and damage public trust in scholarly research.

Risk Area: Technical

Technological and operational limitations

Many institutions face significant resource limitations, both in staffing and technological infrastructure, which hinder their ability to digitise and manage open access collections. Operational challenges such as inadequate metadata, insufficient procedural workflows, and technical vulnerabilities are commonly cited as barriers to effectively securing and maintaining accessible digital collections.

"Open datasets must be refined from all personal and institutional secret information before publishing. Unrefined datasets will compromise technical-system vulnerabilities (e.g. IP and digital address info). Last but not least, wrong-indexed datasets may cause plagiarism."

Research Institution, Turkey

Key Risks

- Limited resources for digitisation, digital preservation and open access management including insufficient funding, staffing, skills to maintain, and provide reliable access to digital collections.
- Challenges with metadata quality and technological infrastructure, such as inconsistent or incomplete metadata, legacy systems, limited interoperability, and other technical constraints.
- Vulnerabilities in securing and maintaining digital collections including risks related to cybersecurity, data loss, system failures, and the ongoing effort required to ensure continuity over time.
- High-volume, automated scraping by AI bots generating sudden, swarming traffic that exceeds system design assumptions, overwhelms servers, degrades performance or causes outages, distorts analytics, and creates escalating infrastructure costs.

Related mitigation strategies

For crisis preparedness, access continuity, and infrastructure resilience in contexts of political instability, conflict, or environmental disruption, see the [Geopolitical Risk Area](#).

- **Streamline metadata practices:** Implement flexible, layered metadata frameworks that accommodate diverse cultural heritage works, support ongoing enhancement, and reflect ethical and community considerations, while applying standardised metadata practices to improve data quality and searchability, even where resources are constrained.
- **Use open-source software or third-party platforms:** Where budget constraints exist, consider open-source solutions or third-party platforms (such as [Flickr Commons ↗](#), [Wikimedia Commons ↗](#), or [KC Works for Institutions ↗](#)) for managing and displaying digital collections.
- **Allocate staff roles for digital collections:** Designate specific staff or train existing personnel to manage open access collections, even if as a shared responsibility.
- **Plan for long-term digital stewardship:** Adopt organisation-wide digital strategies that cover collections, platforms, staffing, funding, and partnerships – not just individual projects or systems. Digital preservation and resilience depends on continuity of people, skills, and decision-making as much as on infrastructure.
- **Ensure ongoing software maintenance:** Allocate time and staffing for regular software and security maintenance, not only server patching but also application-level updates and code health. Extended periods without substantive maintenance (e.g. two years or more) should be treated as a risk indicator triggering review, resourcing, or migration planning.
- **Reduce single-person and single-vendor dependency:** Ensure more than one staff member or contractor is familiar with core systems and workflows. Maintain documentation, handover plans, and succession arrangements to reduce vulnerability to staff loss or sudden budget cuts.

- **Align with Trustworthy Digital Repository principles:** Where applicable, follow [Trustworthy Digital Repository ↗](#) (TDR) guidance, or community frameworks such as COAR's [Good Practices in Repositories ↗](#), including organisational infrastructure for maintenance, contingency planning, and continuous monitoring to determine when contingency plans should be executed.
- **Ensure regular security audits:** Schedule regular reviews of digital infrastructure to identify and address technical vulnerabilities.
- **Treat AI training-related scraping as a persistent operational risk** requiring improved monitoring, realistic infrastructure planning, and carefully balanced mitigation strategies, rather than relying on voluntary signals or restrictive access measures that undermine open access goals.
- **Explore pay-to-crawl technical systems** to automate compensation for when digital cultural heritage content is accessed by machines.

- **Training and guidelines on how to build low-cost digitising facilities and how to maintain the data:**
 - [Mobile Digitising \(MobiDig\) project online platform](#) ↗ offering an open and innovative training on the topic for librarians, archivists, managers of small organizations and Vocational Education and Training (VET) teachers in the field of library science.
 - Pavis, M., Wallace, A., Saunders, S. (2023) [Doing Digitisation on a Budget: A Guide to Low-Cost Digital Projects](#) ↗, supported by [The National Lottery Heritage Fund](#) ↗.
- **Training and guidelines on digital preservation:**
 - Digital Preservation Southampton - [Training](#) ↗: They offer regular workshops providing hands-on experience and introducing attendees to key frameworks in fields across digital preservation, records management, and digital forensics.
 - Digital Preservation Coalition's [resources](#) ↗ for supporting digital preservation activities.
- **Open source collection management systems:** There are options that offer cost-effective solutions for managing digital collections.
 - [Access to Memory \(AtoM\)](#) ↗ - web-based, open source application for standards-based archival description and access in a multilingual, multi-repository environment.
 - [Omeka](#) ↗ - open-source web publishing platforms for sharing digital collections and creating media-rich online exhibits.
 - [CollectionSpace](#) ↗ - web-based, open-source collections management software for cultural heritage organizations, museums & more.
 - [Tainacan](#) ↗ - open source, flexible and powerful repository platform for creating digital archives in WordPress.
 - [Thoth](#) ↗ - non-profit, open metadata management and dissemination platform.
- **Metadata standards and principles:** Using consistent metadata standards and principles aids in interoperability and usability of online collections.

- [FAIR principles](#) ↗ are a set of guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. The principles emphasise machine-actionability (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data.
- [Dublin Core](#) ↗ Metadata Terms is a general purpose metadata vocabulary for describing resources of any type. The Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) is responsible for maintaining the Dublin Core vocabulary.
- [International Image Interoperability Framework \(IIIF\)](#) ↗ is a set of open standards for delivering high-quality, attributed digital images and audio/visual files from servers to different environments on the Web where they can then be viewed and interacted with in many ways.
- GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Image and Metadata Handbook for Wikimedia Commons](#) ↗
- GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Sandbox Template for Wikimedia Commons Metadata Management](#) ↗
- Collections Trust's Digitising Collections Resources - [What information should I record?](#) ↗ includes a set of frameworks, guides and signposts of other resources.
- **CC Signals:** Explore Creative Commons' [preference signals framework](#) ↗ (a simple pact between creators and AI developers), review the [implementation proposal](#) ↗, and [share your feedback](#) ↗.
- **Pay-to-Crawl:** Explore [where CC Stands on Pay-to-Crawl](#) ↗.

Good Practices

- [Tainacan Showcase](#) ↗
- [Flickr Commons Members](#) ↗
- [Partial list of the GLAM-Wikimedia collaboration projects](#) ↗
- [Low-cost digitisation ideas from real life projects](#) ↗ in Pavis, M., Wallace, A., Saunders, S. (2023) [Doing Digitisation on a Budget: A Guide to Low-Cost Digital Projects](#) ↗, supported by [The National Lottery Heritage Fund](#) ↗.

How this risk area connects to other risk areas

Technical capacity is a foundation for legal compliance, ethical stewardship, financial sustainability, and geopolitical resilience. Weak infrastructure, undocumented systems, or staff dependency increase exposure to data loss, service outages, legal non-compliance, and political disruption. Conversely, investments in open standards, preservation workflows, redundancy, and staff capacity strengthen the institution's ability to sustain open access even under financial constraints or external pressure.

Use cases

Research data managers don't make datasets open access, because inadequate or technically misleading data may spread rapidly and be misinterpreted. This can negatively impact the credibility of the research institution and result in difficulties securing future funding.

Digital archivists don't make raw datasets open access, because unrefined data might contain sensitive personal or institutional information. This could lead to security breaches or exploitation of system vulnerabilities, affecting the safety and privacy of both the institution and its stakeholders.

Risk Area: Financial

Financial constraints and monetisation risks

Financial challenges heavily influence institutions' decisions to adopt open access policies and practices. Concerns about potential revenue loss, particularly for those relying on licensing and sales, are frequently cited. Additionally, the costs associated with implementing and sustaining open access collections further restrict the capacity of some institutions to make their materials publicly and freely accessible.

"We prefer to maintain copyright on the images of our collections as use of images is one of our few income streams."

Museum, United Kingdom

Key Risks

- Financial burden of digitisation, licensing, and maintaining open access infrastructure: Open access activities and services may require significant upfront and ongoing investment in digitisation, rights management, technical infrastructure, and staff expertise, placing pressure on organisational budgets, especially where funding is time-limited or uncertain.
- Costs of transitioning to open access: The pathway to openness can have unanticipated short-term costs related to legacy systems and materials, policy realignment, and staff training, reflecting organisational inertia and the resources required to adopt new practices.
- Hidden operational and integration costs of free open inputs: Even when works are openly licensed and free of direct licensing fees, organisations may incur significant costs related to storage, management, transformation, and integration of materials into existing systems and workflows.
- Unplanned financial liabilities due to legal uncertainty: Unclear licence conditions or incorrect public domain assessments may trigger legal challenges, resulting in unexpected compliance costs and resource diversion.
- Shift in revenue models and value-capture mechanisms: Open access and open licensing may require organisations to move beyond traditional revenue models, relying more on indirect, partnership-based, or reputational forms of value that can be harder to measure, forecast, and integrate into existing financial planning frameworks.

Related mitigation strategies

For guidance on funding continuity, diversification, and reducing reliance on volatile or politically contingent revenue streams, see the [Geopolitical Risk Area](#).

- **Explore low-cost digitisation ideas:** Digitise with smartphones; pilot the work with a small collection; use free platforms to publish materials for any reuse purpose, and low-cost platforms to publish materials with rights restrictions; coordinate a volunteer network to digitise materials; digitise on demand for a small fee.
- **Explore cost savings by adopting open licensing:** Administrative and enforcement costs associated with paid licensing can be reduced by shifting to open licensing models. Savings arise from minimising or eliminating staff time spent on evaluating requests, negotiating fees, and managing agreements, while maintaining broad access to collections and avoiding substantial revenue loss.
- **Leverage indirect revenue and fundraising from open access:** Institutions can use open licensing to complement existing funding and revenue sources by increasing visibility, strengthening narratives of public value, and enabling collaboration. While direct revenue gains from open access may be limited, openness can support fundraising, partnerships, retail activities, and grant acquisition, as well as contribute to cost efficiencies, helping to strengthen overall financial sustainability.
- **Diversify and realign value capture beyond direct licensing revenue:** Reassess the opportunity costs of restrictive access policies and reducing reliance on direct monetisation of digital assets where returns are limited. Emphasising open access to digital collections can support wider audience engagement, partnerships, and social impact, while enabling alternative revenue streams such as collaborations, services, funding support, and mission-aligned commercial activities that better align with contemporary market conditions and institutional goals.
- **Explore funding opportunities** dedicated to digitisation and open access projects and initiatives, which can help reduce financial pressure.

- **Engage in strategic partnerships:** Collaborate with public and private sector partners, as well as third-party platforms and community networks, to share resources, reduce digitisation and infrastructure costs, and extend the reach of digital cultural heritage.
 - **Public-private partnerships** can help minimise upfront digitisation costs, but they require careful contractual design to avoid copyright or licensing arrangements that prioritise revenue generation or restrict open access.
 - **Engagement with external platforms and communities** (e.g. open knowledge or sharing platforms) can reduce infrastructure and hosting costs, while introducing new financial demands related to staff time, skills development, and content preparation. These costs can be mitigated by establishing residency programmes, such as community volunteers or interns (e.g. a [Wikimedian-in-Residence ↗](#)), to support platform engagement, knowledge transfer, and sustainable participation.

- **Training and guidelines on how to build low-cost digitizing facilities and how to maintain the data:**
 - [Mobile Digitizing \(MobiDig\) project online platform ↗](#) offering an open and innovative training on the topic for librarians, archivists, managers of small organizations and Vocational Education and Training (VET) teachers in the field of library science.
 - Pavis, M., Wallace, A., Saunders, S. (2023) [Doing Digitisation on a Budget: A Guide to Low-Cost Digital Projects ↗](#), supported by [The National Lottery Heritage Fund ↗](#).
- **CC Toolkit for Business ↗:** A set of resources to allow professional individuals and organizations understand why the use of CC licenses can be a strategic instrument to consider in their business models.
- McCarthy, D. (2024) Balancing access and income – the dilemma of museum image licensing. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13371244> ↗.
- Meletti, B., Erickson, K., Iramina, A., & Stobo, V. (2025) Open Licensing Models in the Cultural Heritage Sector. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15728474> ↗.

Good Practices

- Pekel, J. (2014) [Democratising the Rijksmuseum ↗](#), Europeana Foundation.
- Pekel, J. (2015) [Making a Big Impact on a Small Budget: How the Livrustkammaren och Skoklosters slott med Stiftelsen Hallwylska museet \(LSH\) Shared their Collection with the World ↗](#), Europeana Foundation.
- Valeonti, F., Hudson-Smith, A., Terras, M. et al. (2018) [Reaping the Benefits of Digitisation: Pilot study exploring revenue generation from digitised collections through technological innovation ↗](#), conference presentation.
- Valeonti, F., Terras, M., Hudson-Smith, A., Zarkali, C. (2019) [Examining Mobile Print-on-Demand as an Alternative to Image Licensing for Monetising Digitisation to Promote OpenGLAM ↗](#).
- [Low-cost digitisation ideas from real life projects ↗](#) in Pavis, M., Wallace, A., Saunders, S. (2023) [Doing Digitisation on a Budget: A Guide to Low-Cost Digital Projects ↗](#), supported by [The National Lottery Heritage Fund ↗](#).

How this risk area connects to other risk areas

Financial decisions shape legal, technical, and policy risk exposure. Reliance on restrictive licensing for revenue can increase legal complexity and ethical tension, while underinvestment in infrastructure heightens technical and geopolitical vulnerability. Diversifying funding sources, reducing dependence on fragile income streams, and aligning value capture with mission-driven openness can enhance institutional resilience and reduce susceptibility to political or market shocks.

Use cases

Publishers don't make all their publications open access, because this would lead to a significant loss of revenue from hard copy sales. This loss impacts the financial sustainability of the journals, especially since they do not charge author processing fees to offset costs.

Repository managers don't make high-resolution image collections fully open access, because unrestricted use could lead to commercial exploitation without compensation. This undermines potential revenue from licensing agreements with partner picture agencies, affecting the institution's funding and financial viability.

Institution administrators don't make all digital assets open access, because without control over usage, there's a risk of images being used in commercial products. This affects revenue streams from licensing, which may be crucial for funding preservation and digitisation projects.

Risk Area: Policy

Policy and risk mitigation development

Studies show that few institutions have comprehensive policies in place to address risks associated with open access, such as data misuse, ethical considerations, and copyright breaches. GLAM professionals emphasise the need for clearer policies and procedural workflows to manage these challenges effectively, and minimise the risks of harm or misrepresentation.

"We are not placing all our collections out there to be available due to lack of procedural workflow in obtaining permissions to digitise and display collection items. This is a missed opportunity."

Library, United States of America

Key Risks

- Lack of formal policies for managing risks associated with open access.
- Insufficient workflows for handling legal, ethical, technical, operational, financial and geopolitical challenges.

Related mitigation strategies

Policy development enables and coordinates mitigation across [Legal](#), [Ethical](#), [Technical](#), [Financial](#), and [Geopolitical](#) Risk Areas. Refer to the relevant sections for domain-specific strategies and guidance.

For policy measures that safeguard institutional autonomy, decision-making authority, and continuity of access during political interference, conflict, or environmental crisis, see the [Geopolitical Risk Area](#).

- **Create a comprehensive open access policy:** Draft a policy that outlines legal, ethical, and technical guidelines for open access. Include clear procedures for rights management, community consultation, and user guidelines.
- **Establish a takedown procedure:** Develop a formal procedure for handling requests to remove or restrict access to certain items.
- **Adopt a risk assessment checklist:** Regularly assess risks and update policies to reflect changing needs, resources, or cultural sensitivities.

- **Open access policy templates:** Available from Creative Commons or GLAM organisations, providing frameworks for developing open access policies.
 - Terms of Use Policy template by the 2024 Policy Template Working Group of the Creative Commons Open Culture Platform [[available in various languages in this Medium article ↗](#)].
 - GLAM-E Lab's [External Open Access Policies ↗](#) document containing a model open access policy designed to be adopted by cultural institutions and organisations and posted on their publicly facing websites.
 - GLAM-E Lab's [Internal Open Access Policies ↗](#) document setting out policies based on laws in the United States and United Kingdom that will help you identify works in your collection that may be good candidates for your open access programme.
- **Takedown policy templates:** Customise a takedown policy template for handling requests to restrict access.
 - [Takedown policy template ↗](#) of the Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM.
 - [D-CRAFT's Writing a Takedown Policy ↗](#).
- **Risk assessment templates:** Use and adapt a risk assessment template to evaluate potential risks before making new materials publicly accessible.
- [Risk assessment template ↗](#) of the Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM.

Good Practices

- [Open Access at The Met ↗](#)
- [Open Access at the Cleveland Museum of Art ↗](#)
- Wellcome Collection: [Policies and Plans ↗](#)
- Wikimedia Foundation: [Open Access Policy ↗](#) | [Licensing policy ↗](#)
- [Yale University Open Access Policy ↗](#)
- Bethel University Library: [SPARK Policies ↗](#) | [Author Copyright Guidelines for SPARK ↗](#) (Digital Commons Institutional Repository)
- [Open Access @ Rhodes University Library ↗](#)
- [Griffith Open Research Statement ↗](#)
- German Archaeological Institute: [Publication Strategy ↗](#) | Data Protection Information
- University of Wyoming Libraries: [Digital Collection Policies ↗](#)
- Emory University: [Open Access Policy ↗](#)
- The Courtauld: [The Courtauld Gallery Collection Online ↗](#) | [Copyright Strategy for Publishing The Witt Library ↗](#)

For more inspiration, check the Open GLAM Survey [version 1.0 ↗](#) and [version 2.0 ↗](#), as well as the [Open GLAM Medium Publication ↗](#).

How this risk area connects to other risk areas

Policy acts as the connective tissue across all risk areas. Without clear policies, workflows, and decision-making frameworks, institutions are forced into reactive responses to legal challenges, ethical concerns, technical failures, financial pressure, or geopolitical interference. Well-defined open access, takedown, and risk assessment policies enable consistent, transparent, and accountable action across all risk dimensions.

Use cases

Collection managers don't make certain items open access, because there is a lack of clear procedural workflows for obtaining permissions. This can result in legal and copyright issues, impacting the institution's ability to share its full range of collections effectively.

Curators at smaller, understaffed institutions don't make all their collections open access, because they lack the resources and trained personnel to manage rights and permissions accurately. This could lead to mismanagement of copyright information, affecting the institution's credibility and the quality of its publicly accessible collections.

Institutional decision makers don't make collections open access, because there is no unified policy or clear leadership direction. This results in inconsistent approaches to monetisation and accessibility, impacting the institution's ability to maintain a cohesive strategy for sharing and protecting its collections.

Risk Area: Geopolitical

Political interference and conflict-driven disruption, natural disasters and environmental pressures

This risk area covers external political and ideologically driven pressures -including those arising from war, conflict, and occupation- that threaten to influence, alter, suppress, or disrupt the online (open) content, presentation, integrity, or availability of cultural heritage collections. Such interference can take many forms, including funding withdrawals, mandated takedowns or revisions, narrative capture (pressure to align collections with particular political or ideological frames), geoblocking, network outages, platform dependency shocks, cyberattacks against collection systems, or physical damage to servers, connectivity infrastructure, and even to the landmarks themselves.

This risk area also explicitly encompasses natural disasters and other environmental pressures, as their consequences for cultural heritage -and for its online (and open) availability- are deeply intertwined with political dynamics. Even when destruction appears to be purely environmental, the aftermath is never neutral: whether something is rebuilt, how it is rebuilt, and whose heritage is prioritised in that process -including decisions about its digital presence and accessibility- are all fundamentally political choices.

- **Loss of autonomy, governance interference, and content suppression:** External actors pressure institutions to align with preferred narratives, compromising curatorial, editorial, and governance independence. This can include sudden funding cuts, freezes, or “efficiency” and cost-saving measures that drastically reduce staff capacity, slow or halt digitisation and preservation programmes, and degrade digital services even when collections nominally remain accessible. In some contexts, enforced changes to boards, directors, or senior leadership (particularly in state-funded institutions) are used to redirect institutional priorities or funds. These pressures may be accompanied by formal or informal directives to remove, geofence (limit viewing to certain countries), or alter materials (especially those addressing contested histories, territories, or documenting abuses) resulting in censorship, weakened institutional autonomy, and long-term erosion of trust.
- **Jurisdictional and geopolitical dependency risks:** Digital heritage stored on servers or cloud infrastructure located in a foreign jurisdiction may become vulnerable if diplomatic or political relations deteriorate. Changes in law, sanctions, access restrictions, or state control over infrastructure can render collections inaccessible, subject to seizure, surveillance, alteration, or forced takedown, even when hosted in countries previously considered “friendly”.
- **Access disruption from war, conflict, or crisis:** Physical damage to data centres, local servers, power grids, or collection storage facilities; telecom blackouts (internet or phone cut-offs); internet traffic rerouting through hostile or unstable infrastructure, making services slow, altered, or unreachable; and supply-chain interruptions delaying repairs, hardware replacement, or digitisation efforts. These disruptions can affect both digital access and the safety of un-digitised physical collections.
- **Cybersecurity and integrity threats:** Targeted ransomware (hackers lock files for payment); data theft (collections or user data stolen); Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS: flooding a site so it goes down); defacement (public pages altered); and integrity attacks (catalog records or files silently changed). Such incidents can corrupt catalogs, finding aids, or digitised objects, undermine authenticity, and damage institutional credibility and public trust.

- **Risk to physical collections and gaps in digitisation:** Where digitisation has not yet occurred (especially for smaller or under-resourced institutions) physical objects remain uniquely vulnerable to destruction, theft, neglect, or decay during conflict, political upheaval, austerity, climate-related events, and natural disasters. Increasingly frequent and severe floods, fires, heatwaves, storms, and seismic events threaten collection storage, buildings, and environmental controls, particularly where resources for adaptation are limited. Delayed or reactive digitisation strategies increase the likelihood of irreversible loss, especially when mass digitisation and preservation programmes are not funded proactively in advance of a crisis.

Governance and policy

Related mitigation strategies

For developing and maintaining open access policies, takedown procedures, risk assessment workflows, and governance frameworks that enable institutions to respond consistently, see the [Policy Risk Area](#).

- **Establish clear governance policies:** Develop long-term (digital) strategies and enforce policies that safeguard the institution's mission and resist undue external influence.
 - Prepare and publish a public statement affirming commitment to artistic/cultural and intellectual freedom of speech, and a clear editorial/takedown policy with public criteria, an appeals route, and a public log of changes.
 - Define risk-based digital access states in advance (e.g. open / limited / embargo / dark archive), and clear criteria for switching between them during a crisis.
 - Ensure governance frameworks, legal agreements, and board-level decisions explicitly permit geo-redundant storage, cross-border replication, and collaboration with trusted external partners. This policy groundwork is essential for technical measures such as multi-provider storage, international mirroring, and emergency access arrangements to function when needed.
- **Run simulated, discussion-based training activities** (tabletop exercises/walk-through drills) where staff or team members talk through how they would respond to hypothetical crisis scenarios, such as censorship pressure, ransomware playbook, prolonged outages, loss of key personnel, fire, earthquake etc.

Technical resilience

Related mitigation strategies

For operational capacity, system maintenance, and long-term sustainability, including staffing continuity, infrastructure maintenance, and digital preservation, see the [Technical Risk Area](#).

- **Geo-redundant preservation:** Keep copies in multiple locations and with multiple providers; follow the 3-2-1 rule (3 copies, 2 types of storage, 1 off-site). Use community replication approaches such as LOCKSS/CLOCKSS (“Lots Of Copies Keep Stuff Safe”).
- **Standards-aligned preservation workflows:** Adopt Open Archival Information System (OAIS)–aligned workflows; record provenance and preservation actions with PREMIS (“Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies”); run regular fixity checks to detect silent corruption; and maintain immutable or air-gapped backups (write-once and offline).
- **Fast failover and degraded-mode access:** Be ready to switch users to backups or read-only services, including Content Delivery Network (CDN)-backed static mirrors, a read-only ‘safe mode’ for catalogs, and low-bandwidth site versions for blackout or degraded connectivity conditions.
- **Zero-trust and segmentation:** Don’t assume any internal system is safe by default; split networks so a breach in public systems can’t reach preservation storage. Apply least-privilege access, multi-factor authentication (MFA) login, and privileged access management for administrators.
- **DDoS protection and continuity access:** Protect portals and APIs (machine-to-machine interfaces) with anti-DDoS services, web application firewalls (WAF), and rate limiting (limits on request bursts). Provide offline or bulk export options when systems are degraded or unavailable.

Legal and partnership safeguards

Related mitigation strategies

For copyright compliance, licensing clarity, contractual safeguards, and approaches to managing jurisdictional and platform-related legal risks, see the [Legal Risk Area](#).

- **License and host diversity:** Avoid single-vendor lock-in; include data-portability and exit clauses in contracts; keep off-platform discovery via interoperable protocols such as OAI-PMH (harvesting protocol) and IIIF (standard for interoperable images) to ensure collections remain findable even if primary platforms fail.
- **Formalise external partnerships:** Maintain memoranda of understanding with trusted international repositories, preservation networks, and web-archiving partners to support emergency mirroring, custody transfer, or access continuity.
- **Map jurisdictional exposure:** Maintain a clear map of where data is stored, which legal regimes apply, and how traffic is routed, including exposure to sanctions, data sovereignty rules, or infrastructure control changes.

Funding

Related mitigation strategies

For strategies on financial sustainability, diversification of income, and moving beyond traditional revenue streams, see the [Financial Risk Area](#).

- **Diversify funding sources:** Seek a mix of public, private, philanthropic, and community funding to reduce reliance on volatile or politically contingent sources.
- **Maintain a continuity fund:** Keep a modest, protected fund for preservation storage, emergency maintenance, incident response, and short-term staffing continuity during crises.

Transparency and community

Related mitigation strategies

For ethical guidance on community engagement, narrative integrity, culturally sensitive representation, and accountability in the use and reuse of collections, see the [Ethical Risk Area](#).

- **Document and disclose changes:** Keep detailed records of any access restrictions, content alterations or removals to preserve institutional history and provide context for future reference; share annual integrity and availability metrics (e.g., fixity pass rates, uptime) to maintain trust.
- **Establish a crisis communications plan** (roles, press representatives, message templates, disclosure timelines) for addressing the press or complaints from partners and the public.
- **Engage in advocacy:** Collaborate with professional associations, advocacy groups and communities of practice to learn from the experience of others, and collectively address and respond to geopolitical pressures.

- **Risk assessment templates:** Use and adapt a risk assessment template to register and evaluate real or potential vulnerabilities to political and ideological interference.
 - [Risk assessment template](#) ↗ of the Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM.
 - [Repository Crisis Scorecards](#) ↗ to measure how resilient a repository might be in its normal state and during certain crises. This includes a measure of how well a repository might weather an example crisis, how easy it might be to restore metadata, and how much societal impact a missing repository would have.
- **Policy development guides:** Access resources for crafting governance policies that reinforce institutional autonomy.
 - [Museum Best Practices for Managing Controversy](#) ↗ includes a “Freedom of Speech Commitment” template, steps to prepare in advance for potential controversy, and procedures for addressing the press or complaints from the public.
 - [Publication by MBR regarding the “culture wars” from the far-right in memorials and museums](#) ↗ (in German, includes recommendations to prepare in advance for potential controversy, and procedures for addressing the press or complaints from the public).
- **ARCHES (At-Risk Cultural Heritage Series)** ↗ – Thematic series exploring endangered cultural heritage around the world. The continuous nature of the problem of endangered and destroyed cultural heritage, and the fact that it is not limited to far-away countries in political disarray, underscores the importance of training on historical examples and the legal frameworks that exist to protect important works and sites.
- Wikipedia essay: [There is a deadline](#) ↗ is a page containing the advice or opinions of one or more Wikipedia contributors, who warn that the preservation of the world’s knowledge is at stake, and encourage everyone to contribute to Wikipedia before it’s too late.
- [Learning Lessons from the Cyber-Attack](#) ↗ (8 March 2024) by Sir Roly Keating, Chief Executive of the British Library.
- [Learning from Cyberattacks](#) ↗ (14 November 2024) by Brewster Kahle, Founder of the Internet Archive.

- [Lessons from a Cyberattack: The National Museum of the Royal Navy's Journey Through Crisis and Recovery](#) ↗ (27 September 2025) by Manuel Charr.

Good Practices

- [SUCHO: Saving Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Online](#) is an initiative of over 1,500 international volunteers who are collaborating online to digitise and preserve Ukrainian cultural heritage. Since the start of the invasion, SUCHO has web-archived more than 5,000 websites and 50TB of data of Ukrainian cultural institutions, to prevent these websites from going offline. The websites range from national archives to local museums, from 3D tours of churches to children's art centers.
- [Safeguarding Research & Culture](#) is creating an alternative infrastructure for archiving and disseminating cultural heritage and scientific knowledge. They seek to preserve cultural memory in a way that traditional archives cannot, so as to ensure that our cultural, intellectual and scientific heritage exists in multiple copies, in multiple places, and that no single entity or group of entities can make it all disappear.
- [Data Rescue Project](#) is a coordinated effort of three data organizations, including members of IASSIST, RDAP, and the Data Curation Network, with the aim to serve as a clearinghouse for data rescue-related efforts and data access points for public US governmental data that are currently at risk. Efforts include: data gathering, data curation and cleaning, data cataloging, and providing sustained access and distribution of data assets.
- [UChicago Data Mirror](#) is a platform that provides convenient access to public datasets that are frequently used in academic research and education at the University of Chicago.
- The Clark Art Institute in Williamstown, Massachusetts issued a [statement](#) disapproving the reuse of Jean-Léon Gérôme's painting "Slave Market" (1866) by the German right-wing party Alternative für Deutschland (AfD), while still enacting an Open Access policy, allowing for any reproduction of a public domain work to be downloaded high-resolution for free, as expressed in their [FAQ page](#).
- Advocacy networks and coalitions supporting cultural institutions in navigating political challenges:

- [SAVE the NEA! Restore NEH and IMLS!](#) ↗ is a call-to-action urging people to contact the U.S. Congress to protect and fully restore federal funding and staffing for the National Endowment for the Arts (NEA), the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS). The campaign highlights recent cuts that have left these cultural agencies unable to fulfill their mandates supporting arts, humanities, libraries and museums across every state and territory, and emphasises the economic and community benefits of this federal investment.
- [Advocate Alert Trump Budget Proposes Billions in Cuts, Including Elimination of IMLS, NEH and NEA](#) ↗ is an advocacy alert about a proposed U.S. federal budget that would cut billions in domestic spending and eliminate funding for three key cultural agencies – the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS), the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), and the National Endowment for the Arts (NEA). The alert highlights the potential impact on museums, libraries, arts, and humanities programmes and encourages readers to contact Congress to support continued funding for these agencies.

How this risk area connects to other risk areas

Geopolitical risks rarely create new vulnerabilities; instead, they expose and accelerate existing ones. Legal ambiguity, ethical uncertainty, technical fragility, financial dependency, and weak governance become acute under political pressure, conflict, or environmental crisis. ***Mitigation strategies in this area therefore function as stress tests for the effectiveness of measures implemented across all other risk areas.***

Use cases

A publicly funded institution restricts access to sensitive digital materials because political pressure and funding controls are used to reshape governance and priorities, impacting curatorial autonomy, staff capacity, and long-term trust in the collection.

An institution relies on foreign-hosted cloud infrastructure for its digital collections, because it is cost-effective and previously considered low-risk. When geopolitical relations shift, legal and political controls restrict access or impose takedowns, impacting collection integrity, autonomy, and availability.

A cultural heritage institution relies on local data centres, servers, and on-site collection storage to provide access to its digital and physical collections. When war or crisis damages power, telecom, and storage infrastructure, and disrupts supply chains, digital services become unreachable and undigitised physical collections are placed at heightened risk, impacting access, preservation, and institutional continuity.

Other Risk Areas

Related risks and concerns beyond open access

Some risks and concerns identified in the literature extend beyond the primary objectives of this Toolkit, which focuses on open access to digital cultural heritage collections. These include broader issues such as online privacy and security, especially in the wake of increased digital engagement during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, and safeguarding children and young people when engaging with digital heritage content. Below is a brief overview of these risks, along with pointers to relevant resources that can offer guidance and support.

Online privacy and security

As heritage organizations increasingly operate online, the COVID-19 pandemic has further underscored the need to safeguard privacy and secure digital information. Ensuring the privacy of individuals within the heritage sector and protecting sensitive data are critical as organizations adapt to remote and online workflows.

The guide [Online Privacy and Security ↗](#) (2020), developed by [Naomi Korn Associates ↗](#) for the National Lottery Heritage Fund's [Digital Skills for Heritage ↗](#) initiative, addresses these challenges. It offers checklists, practical advice, and resources to help heritage organizations understand and manage their online activities securely.

Working safely online with children and young people

Digital heritage presents exciting opportunities for children and young people to explore, create, and connect. As GLAM organisations expand their online engagement with communities, it is essential to prioritise the safety of younger audiences, regardless of whether the institution explicitly serves youth.

The guide [Working with Children and Young People Online ↗](#) (2020), produced by [Childnet International ↗](#) for the National Lottery Heritage Fund's [Digital Skills for Heritage ↗](#) initiative, provides practical advice for managing online activities safely. It highlights strategies to mitigate risks and foster safe and creative digital interactions for young audiences.

Use Cases

Scenarios for risks associated with going open

This section captures potential risks associated with opening access to digital cultural heritage collections. Each use case highlights real-world scenarios faced by GLAM organisations, featuring key personas, underlying causes, and potential impacts. Each use case is structured as follows:

 [Persona] doesn't make [X type] collection or work open access, because [Y] will happen and that has an impact on [Z].

These use cases are drawn from responses to open-ended questions in the Working Group's [online survey](#) on risk management in open access to digital collections, as well as from community feedback on the draft *Geopolitical Risks* section received during the public consultation period (October, 22 – November, 30 2025).

A variety of personas are included to represent the diverse roles involved in managing digital collections within GLAM organisations, and sharing them openly with the public.

The use cases are listed below by collection type and risk areas. Click on the arrow (>) to expand each section.

By Risk Areas

✓ Legal

⚠ Cultural heritage professionals don't make certain digital collections open access because of copyright ambiguity. If materials are made available without proper copyright checks, there's a risk of copyright infringement or misuse by the public, which can impact legal compliance and damage the reputation of the institution.

⚠ Decision makers don't make certain digital collections open access, because inaccurate licensing or uncertainties in copyright ownership could lead to privacy breaches or unauthorised sharing or misuse. This would impact the institution's ability to safeguard sensitive cultural materials and comply with contractual obligations, especially in cases involving Indigenous communities.

✓ **Ethical**

⚠ Digital collection managers don't make certain culturally sensitive audio and video materials open access, because there's a risk of them being exploited for commercial purposes without permission. This could disrespect the cultural heritage of the content and negatively affect the institution's relationships with content owners and the public.

⚠ Data managers don't make certain open datasets available without restrictions, because the information could be misused for illicit excavations or fuel conspiracy theories. This misuse can lead to cultural misinformation and damage public trust in scholarly research.

⚠ Curators don't make Indigenous collections open access, because there is a risk of unethical sharing without proper decolonial protocols. This could lead to cultural exploitation and disrespect towards the communities, undermining trust and collaboration with Indigenous partners.

⚠ Institution managers don't make certain heritage photographs open access, because of potential self-image rights violations and misuse for commercial purposes. This can harm the dignity of the individuals depicted and damage the institution's commitment to ethical and respectful representation.

✓ **Technical**

⚠ Research data managers don't make datasets open access, because inadequate or technically misleading data may spread rapidly and be misinterpreted. This can negatively impact the credibility of the research institution and result in difficulties securing future funding.

⚠ Digital archivists don't make raw datasets open access, because unrefined data might contain sensitive personal or institutional information. This could lead to security breaches or exploitation of system vulnerabilities, affecting the safety and privacy of both the institution and its stakeholders.

✓ **Financial**

⚠ Repository managers don't make high-resolution image collections fully open access, because unrestricted use could lead to commercial exploitation without compensation. This undermines potential revenue from licensing agreements with partner picture agencies, affecting the institution's funding and financial viability.

⚠ Institution administrators don't make all digital assets open access, because without control over usage, there's a risk of images being used in commercial products. This affects revenue streams from licensing, which may be crucial for funding preservation and digitisation projects.

⚠ Publishers don't make all their publications open access, because this would lead to a significant loss of revenue from hard copy sales. This loss impacts the financial sustainability of the journals, especially since they do not charge author processing fees to offset costs.

✓ **Policy**

△ Institutional decision makers don't make collections open access, because there is no unified policy or clear leadership direction. This results in inconsistent approaches to monetization and accessibility, impacting the institution's ability to maintain a cohesive strategy for sharing and protecting its collections.

△ Collection managers don't make certain items open access, because there is a lack of clear procedural workflows for obtaining permissions. This can result in legal and copyright issues, impacting the institution's ability to share its full range of collections effectively.

△ Curators at smaller, understaffed institutions don't make all their collections open access, because they lack the resources and trained personnel to manage rights and permissions accurately. This could lead to mismanagement of copyright information, affecting the institution's credibility and the quality of its publicly accessible collections.

△ Institutional decision makers don't make collections open access, because there is no unified policy or clear leadership direction. This results in inconsistent approaches to monetisation and accessibility, impacting the institution's ability to maintain a cohesive strategy for sharing and protecting its collections.

✓ Geopolitical

△ A publicly funded institution restricts access to sensitive digital materials because political pressure and funding controls are used to reshape governance and priorities, impacting curatorial autonomy, staff capacity, and long-term trust in the collection.

△ An institution relies on foreign-hosted cloud infrastructure for its digital collections, because it is cost-effective and previously considered low-risk. When geopolitical relations shift, legal and political controls restrict access or impose takedowns, impacting collection integrity, autonomy, and availability.

△ A cultural heritage institution relies on local data centres, servers, and on-site collection storage to provide access to its digital and physical collections. When war or crisis damages power, telecom, and storage infrastructure, and disrupts supply chains, digital services become unreachable and undigitised physical collections are placed at heightened risk, impacting access, preservation, and institutional continuity.

△ A small, regionally funded organisation does not make its physical collections and associated digital records open access or prioritise mass digitisation, because of limited resources and competing short-term priorities. When armed conflict disrupts power, telecommunications, and local infrastructure, undigitised collections and locally stored digital files become inaccessible or are damaged, impacting long-term preservation, international access, and the institution's ability to safeguard cultural heritage during and after the conflict.

△ An organisation offers open access to its collections without adequate security and integrity controls. When cyberattacks compromise systems or data, collection authenticity and public trust are damaged, and access is disrupted.

△ An organisation records preservation actions but does not invest in regular software maintenance, because systems appear stable and cost savings are prioritised. After several years without updates, technical debt and security risks force the system offline, impacting access, preservation continuity, and institutional resilience.

By Collection Type

✓ **All types of works and collections**

△ Cultural heritage professionals don't make certain digital collections open access because of copyright ambiguity. If materials are made available without proper copyright checks, there's a risk of copyright infringement or misuse by the public, which can impact legal compliance and damage the reputation of the institution.

△ Decision makers don't make certain digital collections open access, because inaccurate licensing or uncertainties in copyright ownership could lead to privacy breaches or unauthorised sharing or misuse. This would impact the institution's ability to safeguard sensitive cultural materials and comply with contractual obligations, especially in cases involving Indigenous communities.

△ Library administrators don't make certain collections open access, because many of them have not been digitised. This delays public access and impacts the institution's ability to share resources effectively in the digital age.

△ Collection managers don't make certain items open access, because there is a lack of clear procedural workflows for obtaining permissions. This can result in legal and copyright issues, impacting the institution's ability to share its full range of collections effectively.

△ Curators at smaller, understaffed institutions don't make all their collections open access, because they lack the resources and trained personnel to manage rights and permissions accurately. This could lead to mismanagement of copyright information, affecting the institution's credibility and the quality of its publicly accessible collections.

△ Institutional decision makers don't make collections open access, because there is no unified policy or clear leadership direction. This results in inconsistent approaches to monetisation and accessibility, impacting the institution's ability to maintain a cohesive strategy for sharing and protecting its collections.

△ A publicly funded institution restricts access to sensitive digital materials because political pressure and funding controls are used to reshape governance and priorities, impacting curatorial autonomy, staff capacity, and long-term trust in the collection.

△ An institution relies on foreign-hosted cloud infrastructure for its digital collections, because it is cost-effective and previously considered low-risk. When geopolitical relations shift, legal and political controls restrict access or impose takedowns, impacting collection integrity, autonomy, and availability.

△ A cultural heritage institution relies on local data centres, servers, and on-site collection storage to provide access to its digital and physical collections. When war or crisis damages power, telecom, and storage infrastructure, and disrupts supply chains, digital services become unreachable and undigitised physical collections are placed at heightened risk, impacting access, preservation, and institutional continuity.

✓ **Indigenous collections**

△ Curators don't make Indigenous collections open access, because there is a risk of unethical sharing without proper decolonial protocols. This could lead to cultural exploitation and disrespect towards the communities, undermining trust and collaboration with Indigenous partners.

✓ **Audiovisual materials**

△ Institution managers don't make certain heritage photographs open access, because of potential self-image rights' violations and misuse for commercial purposes. This can harm the dignity of the individuals depicted, and damage the institution's commitment to ethical and respectful representation.

△ Repository managers don't make high-resolution image collections fully open access, because unrestricted use could lead to commercial exploitation without compensation. This undermines potential revenue from licensing agreements with partner picture agencies, affecting the institution's funding and financial viability.

△ Institution administrators don't make all digital assets open access, because without control over usage, there's a risk of images being used in commercial products. This affects revenue streams from licensing, which may be crucial for funding preservation and digitisation projects.

△ Digital collection managers don't make certain culturally sensitive audio and video materials open access, because there's a risk of them being exploited for commercial purposes without permission. This could disrespect the cultural heritage of the content and negatively affect the institution's relationships with content owners and the public.

✓ **Publications**

△ Publishers don't make all their publications open access, because this would lead to a significant loss of revenue from hard copy sales. This loss impacts the financial sustainability of the journals, especially since they do not charge author processing fees to offset costs.

✓ **Datasets**

△ Data managers don't make certain open datasets available without restrictions, because the information could be misused for illicit excavations or fuel conspiracy theories. This misuse can lead to cultural misinformation and damage public trust in scholarly research.

△ Research data managers don't make datasets open access, because inadequate or technically misleading data may spread rapidly and be misinterpreted. This can negatively impact the credibility of the research institution and result in difficulties securing future funding.

△ Digital archivists don't make raw datasets open access, because unrefined data might contain sensitive personal or institutional information. This could lead to security breaches or exploitation of system vulnerabilities, affecting the safety and privacy of both the institution and its stakeholders.

Templates

Customisable templates for risk management when going open

The templates below are designed to support the implementation of selected mitigation strategies associated with the key risk areas outlined in this Toolkit.

They are intended to assist GLAM professionals in putting these strategies into practice and can be tailored and adapted to suit different organisational contexts when establishing open access to digital collections.

The available templates are listed below:

- [Risk Assessment template](#)
- [Takedown Policy template](#)
- [Feedback Form template](#)

Risk Assessment

Risk Assessment Template

How to use this template?

The Risk Assessment Template can be customised to suit specific projects for opening access to digital cultural heritage collections.

1. **Identify risks:** List potential risks, noting their descriptions and categories.
2. **Analyse risks:** Assess each risk's likelihood and potential impact to assign an overall risk rating.
3. **Evaluate and prioritise:** Rank risks based on their risk rating and impact on operations, assigning priority levels to focus on the most critical.
4. **Develop mitigation strategies:** Define measures for each risk, specifying responsible parties and needed resources.
5. **Monitor and review:** Track each risk's status and regularly review to update mitigation measures and priorities as needed.

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Takedown Policy

Takedown Policy Template

How to use this template

This template provides a comprehensive framework for a takedown policy, ensuring that your GLAM institution can respond appropriately to requests while protecting its interests and those of copyright holders. You can customise this template accordingly.

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Feedback Form

Feedback Form Template

How to use this template

This form allows users to report any issues, concerns, or potential risks they encounter while using your institution's online collections. You can customise this template accordingly.

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Risk-Strategy Interrelation Matrix

Illustrating how key risk areas are interrelated, as strategies adopted to mitigate risks in one area may shift, intensify, or introduce risks in others.

Icon key (risk areas)

- Legal
- Ethical
- Technical
- Financial
- Policy
- Geopolitical

This matrix is indicative rather than exhaustive.

Risk area	Key risk	Mitigation strategy	Benefits	Challenges	Interrelated risks
 Policy					
 Financial					
 Technical					
 Technical					

 Technical					
 Legal					
 Policy					
 Technical					

 Financial					
 Policy					
 Geopolitical					
 Geopolitical					

 Policy					
 Technical					
 Financial					
 Technical					

<p> Financial</p>					
<p> Legal</p>					
<p> Ethical</p>					

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Related Resources

Indicative resources which can help with understanding the open GLAM landscape and identifying risks and strategies for GLAM organisations in opening up their collections.

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GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Internal Open Access Policies ↗](#).

GLAM-E Lab (2024) [External Open Access Policies ↗](#).

GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Selecting an Alternative Label or Licence ↗](#).

GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Image and Metadata Handbook for Wikimedia Commons ↗](#).

GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Sandbox Template for Wikimedia Commons Metadata Management](#) ↗.

GLAM-E Lab (2024) [Glossary](#) ↗.

GLAM-E Lab (2025) [Are AI Bots Knocking Cultural Heritage Offline?](#) ↗

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Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (2019) [Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data: Reconciling Risks and Benefits for Data Re-use Across Societies](#) ↗. Paris, France: OECD.

Pavis, M., Wallace, A., Saunders, S. (2023) [Doing Digitisation on a Budget: A Guide to Low-Cost Digital Projects ↗](#), supported by [The National Lottery Heritage Fund ↗](#).

Popham, M. (2024) [An Introduction to Disentangling Digital Preservation Risk with CHARM ↗](#). Digital Preservation Coalition Blog.

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Wallace A., Weinberg, M. (2023) [Open Licensing: A Digital Heritage Licensing Briefing ↗](#), supported by The National Lottery Heritage Fund.

Toolkit Outreach

Upcoming

March 26, 2026

RLUK26 Conference

"Managing Risk, Enabling Openness: A Practical Toolkit for GLAM Professionals"

Presentation of the Risk Management Toolkit v2.0 at the [Research Libraries UK 2026 \(RLUK26\) Virtual Conference: "Stewardship in Challenging Times: The Role of Libraries in Supporting Civic Society"](#) ↗.

Past

February 12, 2026

CC Certificate Open Culture Webinar

"Opening Collections, Managing Risk: A Toolkit for GLAM Institutions"

Presentation of the Risk Management Toolkit v2.0 in the context of the January-April 2026 [CC Certificate course](#) ↗.

January 6, 2026

Blog post: *Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM v2.0 Is Here*

"We're pleased to announce [the release of version 2.0 of the Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM](#) ↗, published in December 2025"

October 30, 2025

GLAM Wiki 2025 Conference

"Expanding Risk Management for Open GLAM Amid Geopolitical Uncertainty"

Lightning talk at the [GLAM Wiki 2025 Conference](#) ↗ | Lisbon.

Part of the session: "[Uncertain Futures, Shared Challenges: Protecting and Safeguarding Open Knowledge](#)" ↗.

October 22, 2025

Open and Engaged 2025 Conference

"From Caution to Care: A Living Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM"

Presentation of the Risk Management Toolkit v1.1 at the [Open and Engaged 2025 Conference: "Who Owns Our Knowledge? Exploring Ownership, Access, and Stewardship of Cultural Heritage in the New Era"](#) ↗, organised by the British Library during the [Open Access Week](#) ↗.

September 16, 2025

Europeana Copyright Office Hours

"Beyond Copyright: A Risk Management Toolkit for Open Culture"

Presentation of the Risk Management Toolkit v1.0 and the research behind it at the [Europeana Copyright Office Hours: Evaluating Risk in Copyright Clearance](#) ↗.

March 13, 2025

CC Open Culture Platform Call

Presentation of the Risk Management Toolkit v1.0 during the March 2025 CC Open Culture Platform Call.

January 15, 2025

Report: *CC's Open Culture Platform 2024 Year in Review*

Presentation of the Risk Management Working Group's outputs in [CC's Open Culture Platform 2024 Year in Review](#) ↗ report.

January 15, 2025

Blog post: *Navigating Risks in Open Access: Insights and Strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions*

[Final report](#) ↗ of the Risk Management Working Group on CC Medium Publication: *We Like to Share*.

December 13, 2024

Risk Management Toolkit v1.0 - Conclusion of Risk Management Working Group

Publication of the Risk Management Toolkit v1.0 on Gitbook and full documentation on Zenodo and KC Works.

Conclusion of the Risk Management Working Group.

June 20, 2024

CC Open Culture Platform Call

Presentation of the Working Group's progress (initial literature review findings and open call to participate in the WG's online survey) during the June 2024 CC Open Culture Platform Call.

May 1, 2024

Formation of Risk Management Working Group of CC Open Culture Platform

Open call for CC Open Culture Platform members to join and participate in the Working Group.

Credits and Licensing

The Risk Management Toolkit for Open GLAM and all accompanying documents were published and are updated on Zenodo and KC Works.

- Full Zenodo record: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14419072> ↗
- Full KC Works collection: <https://works.hcommons.org/collections/oa2ch-risk-management/> ↗

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Writing and editing: [Ilkay Holt](#) ↗, [Revekka Kefalea](#) ↗

Reviewers of version 2.0 (2025)

For Geopolitical risk area

- Prof. [Victoria Grace Richardson-Walden](#) ↗, Director of the [Landecker Digital Memory Lab](#) ↗
- [Wilhelmina Randtke](#) ↗, Head of Libraries Technologies and Systems, Georgia Southern University
- [Maarten Zeinstra](#) ↗, IP Squared

We gratefully acknowledge the participants of the World Café discussion held on October 30, 2025 at the [GLAM Wiki 2025 Conference](#) ↗, within the context of the session [Uncertain Futures, Shared Challenges: Protecting and Safeguarding Open Knowledge](#) ↗, for their insights and meaningful contributions to the draft Geopolitical Risks section. This discussion formed part of the public consultation conducted from October 22 to November 30, 2025.

For overall Toolkit

- [Laura Isabel \(Laurisa\) Sastoque Pabón ↗](#), University of Southampton

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Members of the working group during that period –Issahaku Tidoo Abass, Olubusola Afolabi, Khali Allahmagani, Mohammed Awal Awal, Maxwell Beganim, René Bile, Ester Cornelio, Ruby Damenshie-Brown, Christina Haule, Edward Jacobo, Crispin Ngakani, Ngozi Perpetua Osuchukwu– were consulted throughout the development of the Toolkit. The co-leadership of the working group was financially supported by Creative Commons.

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- Toolkit documentation and reports
- Acknowledgments, contributor lists, and credits

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